

Effect of Reinforcing Steel on Ultrasonic Waves when Measuring Compressive Strength of the Concrete

Suad Mohammed Heil* & Maha Seger Ali

*Al- Mussaib Technical Institute, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University,
51009 Babylon, Iraq*

***Email**

ce.smh71@gmail.com (Suad Mohammed Heil)

Abstract

In this study, the relationship between the direction of reinforcing steel and the velocity of wave pulses using ultrasound was studied. The first model represents the slab with (50 x 50 x 15) cm dimensions, the number of models was 4, the reinforcing steel distribution in one direction, diameter (12, 16 mm) and spacing (10, 15) cm. The second model is cubes of dimensions (15 × 15 × 15 cm) and their number 20, and measuring pulse speed in concrete models in a vertical and parallel direction with reinforcing steel. In addition, through the results obtained from the test and the rate of readings was two to each model age (7, 28) days respectively. The effect of reinforcing steel more when it was parallel to the direction of the flow of the wave. And, by increasing the diameter of the reinforcing steel, and when the spacing between the bars reduced. The results obtained from the examination were the increase in the readings for 7 days. The direct method, parallel with the reinforcing steel, for the diameter of 12 mm with spacing (10, 15), readers are (6.5%, 5.3%). When the diameter of 16 mm and for 28 days (7.8%, 5.5%), Also (12) mm and distance (10.15), the results (7%, 6.1%), as well as diameter 16 mm (8.1%, 6.3%) compared to the vertical direction.

Keywords: Component; Formatting; Style; Styling; Insert

1. Introduction

Non-destructive tests, are the method through which the concrete properties can be known at the site, or laboratory without the need to damage part of the building or model, and is the best way to reach specific results on the ability of concrete in the site, the areas of their use have been expanded in locating the blanks and reinforcing steel in the concrete and the concrete cover thickness in the structure. The determination of these factors is no less important than determining the durability of concrete.

In addition, that the use of non-destructive tests and especially the method of ultrasonic in the evaluation of the structures is one of the important ways. Based on what has been mentioned, the decision to

accept or reject or to resort to a more accurate method of examination of the structures is achieved by the ultrasonic test, which is a non-destructive test.

That the method concerning ultrasonic oscillations depends on the sending of inaudible vibrations at a frequency higher than 15 Hz on the part to be examined and received directly and indirectly and then calculate the speed of Ultrasonic vibrations inside the concrete.

There are two situations to place the reinforcing steel in the concrete. [1]

The first case: Is when the axis of the reinforcing steel parallel to the line of flow. In this case, the first wave out directed and go to walk through the reinforcing steel in the region in which. In this case, applies the correction coefficient as shown in fig (1).

Fig (1) Axis of reinforcing steel parallel to the direction of the wave

The second case: is that the axis of the reinforcing steel is vertical to the path of the pulses. In this case, the reading is affected by the diameter of reinforcing steel that is in the path obstructed; a correction coefficient is applied based on the diameters of reinforcing steel as shown in figure (2).

Pulse speed is measured as follows:

$$V = L/T \text{ km/sec} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

L=Path length

T= Time of wave transmission.

A special calibration curve is used to find the resistance of the equivalent cube pressure. This curve was based on the test of a large group of models with different resistances and measured the speed of the pulses in each case. The accuracy results range from 20% to the actual value of the pressure resistance as shown in figure (3).

There are three ways to put the sender and the receiver as shown in figure (4)

The first method is used if the transmitter and the receiver can be placed in this mode, this is the best mode. The second method is to move along the surface in case the possibility of access to only one surface of the tested element and in this case, the process is less efficient than the previous because the largest energy going into the concrete.

The indirect method does not provide information about the weak concrete, which is under the hard surface less accurate and the speed, in this case, less than the directions state. [1]

Some researchers noticed that the increase in the speed of the wave at 28days and in the direct way and parallel to the reinforcing steel compared to the indirect method and models not use reinforcing steel.

The researchers also found a relationship that showed an increase in the speed of Ultrasound waves with increased age, i.e., the speed of the age of (28) days greater than 14 days and the last greater than the age of 7 days. [2]

The British specifications B.S.1881 part203-1986

also stated that, in general reinforcing steel increase the speed of Ultrasonic pulses in concrete, and that the speed of transmission of sound waves depends mainly in the concrete on the diameter of the bars as well as the number and method of distribution of bars in the concrete section, the speed of pulses in reinforcing steel is 5.9 km/s. [3]

Other researchers mentioned that one of the important factors in the effect of measuring the oscillation velocity of the concrete is the presence of the reinforcing steel where the velocity is in reinforcing steel (1.4- 1.7) times more than in conventional or non-reinforced concrete, so reading the velocity in the vicinity of the reinforcing steel is higher than the concrete if a cross-line is crossed with reinforcement, a correction coefficient should be used. This is dependent on the diameter of the reinforcing steel and the density of the reinforcement bars in the tested section. [4]

Also other researcher mentioned that the receiving wave is increased by increasing the diameter of the reinforcing steel and decreasing its decrease and by increasing the distance between the reinforcing steel, thus, the received wave should be calibrated based on the concrete cover and the reinforcing steel, the impact of the reinforcing steel is very low if it is in perpendicular direction to the wave path, but if it is parallel to the wave it is effect more difficult to avoid, therefore, a correction coefficient is used. [5]

The other researchers found that the pulse velocity measured in reinforced concrete in the vicinity of reinforcing bars is usually higher, than in plain concrete of the same composition, this is because the pulse velocity in steel may be up to twice the velocity in plain concrete and under certain conditions, the first pulse to arrive at the receiving transducer travels partly in concrete and partly in steel. [6].

Fig (2) Axis of reinforcing steel perpendicular to the direction of the wave

Fig (3) the relationship between wave speed and pressure resistance

2. Experiments and Materials

Practical side

Includes casting cubes measuring (15x15x15) cm, and casting models in the form of a slab length of 50cm, and width 50 cm, and height 15cm. And the use of bars of 12mm diameter, and 16mm with a change in the distance between bars (10,15) cm, and study the effect on the speed of transmission of Ultrasonic pulses in concrete models, where the compression resistance of cubes is measured at the age of 7 days, and 28day as shown in table (1,2) and figure (6,7).

Materials

1. The mixture used in research. The concrete mix designed to withstand 40 MPa, using the American method and mixing ratios, as shown in the table (3).

2. Cement:

It is the material that possesses the properties of cohesive and adhesive with the present water and these properties make the cementable to bind the metal parts together and turn it into a complete unit and monolithic. The cement type was chosen Aljisir

type is Iraqi Portland cement.

3. Fine aggregate: (sand)

This type of aggregate was supplied from Alakhydar quarry in Karbala governorate, this aggregate was used in concrete mixtures and the results of the laboratory tests carried out on samples of this aggregate were according to the British standard BSI-1881-part203, and table (4) shows the results of the analysis of the sand of Alakhydar quarry, and the percentage of fine materials and sulphates.

4. Coarse aggregate (gravel)

The coarse aggregates originated from AL- Nibaeii quarry, which is located north of Baghdad. This aggregate was used in most of the technical projects of the Al-Musaib technical Institute. The results of the tests conducted in the laboratory of the civil techniques department at the Al- Musaib institute. On samples of this aggregate are shown in table (5) where the results of the examination were compared with the limits of the Iraqi Standard Specification No. 45 1984[7], the coarse aggregate was washed before use in the laboratory and this type was used in concrete mixtures.

Fig (4) Different modes of transmitter and receiver

5. Type of inspection device and method of conducting the examination.

A device known as (Matest, s.r.l, Treviolo) was used to measure the speed of the Ultrasonic oscillations in Figure (5) and in the direct way, i.e., the mode of the transmitter and the receiver on opposite sides of the models to be examined and the indirect way of placing the transmitter and receiver on the same surface according to BS. 1881, part 1: 1970[8].

Fig (5) Ultrasonic device

The model to be examined is removed from the water tank and its surface is thoroughly cleaned, and the length of the pulse path is measured accurately and this length is determined by the device shall be calibrated using a cylinder and special hard metal for this purpose. The ultrasonic velocity is then measured, and the models are left in the laboratory, for the purpose of conducting the examination at the age of 28- days.

3. Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the tests carried out on the models and relationship between the diameter of the reinforcing steel and the velocity of the waves will be discussed. As well as the distance between reinforcing bars and its relationship with the velocity of the Ultrasonic pulses and the factors affecting the test which led to the increase or decrease of Ultrasonic velocity, as well as an effect of age on results.

Where are using Equation No. (2) to calculate the resistance of compression the adoption of the speed of the wave.

$$\text{Concrete strength (Mpa)} = 2.8 \exp(0.53 * v) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where V is the speed and that have been described in equation (1) and through the results, we can conclude the following.

1. Be the effect of steel more when it is parallel to the direction of the validity of the wave.
2. The speed of the waves increases with the increase of the diameter of steel reinforcement bars and increases when the distance between the bars decrease.
3. Non-reinforced concrete cubes give fewer results than the case in which steel reinforcement is found, as shown in the table (6).

The increase in age also increases the speed of Ultrasonic waves due to the reactions of the concrete, where these reactions increase the density of the concrete and thus increase the speed of Ultrasonic

waves in the plain concrete.

As for reinforcing steel, its increase increases the velocity of Ultrasonic waves, the models with steel reinforcing indicate, that the velocity of the waves in the model in which the distance between the steel reinforcing is 10 cm higher than that obtained from the models, 15 cm, i.e., the relationship is inverse. Between the speed of Ultrasonic waves and the distance reinforcing

Also, when compared to reinforced models and the same method of measurement (direct method), they found an increase in a reading of the wave speed by (7%, 6.1%) for the diameter 12mm and age 28 days, as well as an increase of (8.1%, 6.3%) to 16mm diameter with the reinforcing steel spacing (10, 15) cm respectively. Clear in the direction parallel to the flow of the wave because of the transfer velocity of the wave from the transmitter to the receiver in reinforcing steel faster than the vertical direction as shown in the table (7,8,9,10,) and figure (8,9,10,11).

4. Conclusions

1. The effect of reinforcing steel shall be greater when it is parallel to the flow direction of the wave.
2. The impact of the reinforcing steel is limited to the speed of the Ultrasonic pulses when the path of the wave is perpendicular to the reinforcing steel.
3. The greater of the diameter of the reinforcing steel is faster the waves speed and less the distance between reinforcing steel the faster the speed of the waves.
4. The speed of Ultrasound waves obtained from direct tests is greater than that obtained from indirect tests.
5. That the increase in the wave speed in the parallel direction to the vertical direction ranged from (5.3- 8.1).

5. References

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Fig (6) The Compressive Strength at age 7 days Mpa

Fig (7) The Compressive Strength at age 28 days Mpa

Fig (8) The Speed of the wave at age (7, 28) day, diameter (12) mm and distance (10) mm

Fig (9) The Speed of the wave at age (7, 28) day, diameter (12) mm and distance (15) mm

Fig (10) The Speed of the wave at age (7, 28) day, diameter (16) mm and distance (10) mm

Fig (11) The Speed of the wave at age (7, 28) day, diameter (16) mm and distance (15) mm

Table (1): Compressive Strength at age 7 days Mpa

Sample code	Compressive Strength at age 7 days Mpa
S1	24.2
S2	26.45
S3	23.1
S4	22.06
S5	26.91
S6	21.07
S7	26.08
S8	25.54
S9	23.76
S10	26.52
S11	22.07

Table (2): Compressive Strength at Age 28 days Mpa

Sample code	Compressive Strength at Age 28 days Mpa
A1	39.1
A2	36.9
A3	37.02
A4	35.83
A5	37.74
A6	38.14
A7	40.03
A8	36.98
A9	32.09
A10	38.91

Table (3): Concrete mix Design

Cement Kg/m ³	Sand Kg/m ³	Gravel Kg/m ³	Cement /Water Kg/m ³
350	500.5	770	0.43

Table (4): Results of laboratory analysis of fine aggregates, Quarry of Alakhydar.

Sieve Size	Percentage Passing by weight (%)	Specification BSI 1881 -203
4.75	98%	89-100
2.36	85	65-100
1.18	75	45-100
0.6	49	25-80
0.3	12	48-5
0.15	2	15
S03%	0.398	0.5% max.

Table (5): Results of laboratory analysis of coarse aggregates, Quarry of Alnibaieii

Sieve Size	Percentage Passing by weight (%)	Iraqi Specification% No.45,1984
37.5	100	100
19	96.6	90-100
9.5	33.8	30-60
4.75	2.7	0-10
S03%	0.063	0.1 max.

Table (6) Laboratory results for testing of plain concrete

Age(day)	$U_{pv}(m/s)$	Method of test
7	4250	Direct test
7	3130	Indirect test
28	4315	Direct test
28	3420	Indirect test

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Table (7): The speed of the wave (U_{pv} m/s) at age (7, 28) day, diameter 12mm and distance 10 cm.

N0.	Age	Direction	$U_{pv}(m/s)$
1	7 day	parallel	3968
2	7 day	parallel	3756
3	7 day	perpendicular	3642
4	7 day	perpendicular	3611
5	28 day	parallel	4942
6	28 day	parallel	4945
7	28 day	perpendicular	4672
8	28 day	perpendicular	4574

Table (8): The speed of the wave (U_{pv} m/s) at age (7, 28) day, diameter 12mm and distance 15 cm.

N0.	Age	Direction	$U_{pv}(m/s)$
1	7 day	parallel	4253
2	7 day	parallel	4140
3	7 day	perpendicular	3895
4	7 day	perpendicular	3890
5	28 day	parallel	5027
6	28 day	parallel	5123
7	28 day	perpendicular	4700
8	28 day	perpendicular	4690

Table (9): The speed of the wave (U_{px} m/s) at age (7, 28) day, diameter 16mm and distance 10 cm.

N0.	Age	Direction	U_{px} (m/s)
1	7 day	parallel	4253
2	7 day	parallel	4140
3	7 day	perpendicular	3895
4	7 day	perpendicular	3890
5	28 day	parallel	5027
6	28 day	parallel	5123
7	28 day	perpendicular	4700
8	28 day	perpendicular	4690

Table (10): The speed of the wave (U_{px} m/s) at age (7, 28) day, diameter 16mm and distance 15 cm.

N0.	Age	Direction	U_{px} (m/s)
1	7 day	parallel	4019
2	7 day	parallel	3943
3	7 day	perpendicular	3843
4	7 day	perpendicular	3708
5	28 day	parallel	4864
6	28 day	parallel	4790
7	28 day	perpendicular	4537
8	28 day	perpendicular	4560